

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B035
 Date: 28 Jul 2004
 Take Off 13:52:45
 Landing: 18:58:17
 Flight Time 5h05m32

Trials Instructions: ITOP – 146 – DC8 Intercomparison

Operating Area: W of the Azores in a box bounded by 35N and 43N, and 34W and 40W

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Reeves	UEA
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS	Ken Dewey	FAAM
6	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
7	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	WAS-PAN	Ruth Purvis	York University
9	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
10	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
11	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
12	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
13	FAGE	Trevor Ingham	Leeds University
14	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
15			
16			
17			
18			

Track Plot:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B035
 Date: 28th July 2004
 Project: ITOP. DC-8 Intercomparison
 Location: Horta, Azores

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
-----	-----	-----	-----	---	-----
135245		T/O	0.00 kft	269	
135519					ASPs open PSAP flow on
135825	140333	Run 1	9.0 kft	269	
140053					J-W cal complete
140330	141105	Profile 1	9.0 - 16.0 kft		
141135	143522	Run 2	16.0 kft	267	
141800					reset DLUs TWC reset
142137					
143523	144115	Profile 2	16.0 - 22.0 kft	266	
154000					time check with DC-8: identical
joined by DC-8 Science speed 230 KIAS					
154625	155826	Run 3	22.0 kft	255	
160500	161630	Profile 3	22.0 - 12.0 kft	084	
161447					reduced descent to 500ft/min
161630	162829	Run 4	11.9 kft	078	
162851	164853	Profile 4	11.9 - 0.75 kft	079	
163634		interrupt P4	5.0 kft	079	
164005		restart P4	4.9 kft	256	500ft/min
164900	170104	Run 5	1.1 - 1.05 kft	241	
parted from DC-8					
170254	172615	Profile 5	0.68 - 20.0 kft	078	500ft/min PSAP flow off
170400					
171156		restart P5	5.1 kft	077	1000ft/min PSAP flow on
171200					
172827	173302	Profile 6	20.0 - 24.0 kft	253	
173553	175053	Run 6	24.0 kft	074	
175308	175631	Profile 7	24.0 - 21.0 kft	252	
180018	181021	Run 7	20.5 kft	076	
181028	181225	Profile 8	20.5 - 19.0 kft	068	
182149	182409	Profile 9	19.0 - 17.0 kft	086	
182548	184228	Run 8	17.0 kft	087	230 KIAS PSAP flow off
185605					
185817		Land	0.0 kft	269	

B035 Track 28-JUL-04

41°W

39°W

37°W

35°W

33°W

31°W

29°W

27°W

40°N

39°N

38°N

37°N

36°N

40°N

39°N

38°N

37°N

36°N

CTA/KZNY FIR
E FL290-FL410

- Present Flight Level
- Next position on assigned route or OCA entry point
- Estimated time for next position or OCA entry point
- Next subsequent position
- Requested Mach Number, Flight Level, or route
- Further information or clarifying remarks

b) To request a change in Mach Number, or route when a position report message is not appropriate.

Content and Data sequence:

- "Request Clearance"

- Flight identification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
- Requested Mach Number, or route
- Further information or clarifying remarks

REVISED ESTIMATE:

To update time estimate for next position.

Content and Data sequence:

- "Revised Estimate"

- Flight identification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
- Next position of route
- Revised estimate for next position (hours and minutes)
- Further information

WHEN ABLE HIGHER

To pass information on position or time a climb to the next higher FL is acceptable or a clearance for higher FLs is requested when inclusion in a position report message is not appropriate.

Content and Data sequence:

- Flight identification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
- Requested or Acceptable FLs
- at position or time

MISCELLANEOUS MESSAGE:

To pass information or make a request in plain language that does not conform with the content of other message format. No message designator is required as this will be inserted by the ground station.

Content and Data sequence:

- Flight identification (additionally state frequency when using HF)
- General information or request in plain language and format free.

42525
1700Z

28

526nm 4000nm
[1600nm @ Horta
LoHi 1700Z]

ALTIMETER SETTING
Standard pressure setting for cruising flights within OCEANIC FIRs. QNH setting on descent below transition levels.

NEW YORK OCEANIC CTA/KZNY FIR
(Unct'1 below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

SANTA MARIA OCEANIC CTA (A)/LPOO FIR (G)
(Unct'1 below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

38N 38W

1400Z-2000Z
SFC-FL250

35N 40W

+3 = UTC +2 = UTC

P123.45
S 135.825 / 1373.15

DC-8 NASA 817 ETA 1600Z @ RV 38N 38W

BRIEFED LEVELS FL220
SPEED > 270KIAS FL130

4

5

ITOP – 146-DC8 Intercomparison

Mission Scientists: Claire Reeves

Date: 28/7/04

Outline schedule:

08:00 - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

12:00 - Air Crew Briefing

13:15 – Clear aircraft

13:30 – Boarding deadline

14:00 - Take-off

Location: W of the Azores in a box bounded by 35N and 43N, and 34W and 40W.

Aim: To compare data collected on the 146 with that on the DC8 at 3 flight levels.

NOTE: If people wish to perform **zeros or cals** at each comparison level please do so at the **beginning of each run**. Zeros or cals for the first run at FL220 could possibly be performed before the rendez vous. We wish to maximise the time of comparable data.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take off. Climb to first available level (5000ft) to perform a 5 minute run for wet chemistry check (10).
2. T+10 Profile climb at 1000ft/min to FL160 (10).
3. T+20 Straight and level run at 230 kts for 25 minutes for NO_x cals heading towards INBOX (38 22N, 33 22W) (25).
4. T+45 Profile ascent to FL220 and continue to INBOX (15).
5. T+60 Transit to 38N 38W for rendez-vous at 16:00UT (60).
Perform points 6-10 in formation with the DC8 at 230 kts.
6. T+120 Perform a 10-12 minute run in a WSW-ENE orientation (15)
7. T+135 Profile descent at 1000ft/min to FL120 (10)
8. T+145 Perform a 10-12 minute run in a WSW-ENE orientation (15)
9. T+160 Profile descent to 1000ft at 1000ft/min above 5000ft and 500ft/min below (15)
10. T+175 Perform a 10-12 minute run in a WSW-ENE orientation (15)
11. T+190 Profile ascent to FL240 at 500ft/min below ~~500ft~~ 5000 and 1000ft/min above (30).
12. T+220 Perform a run back along a filament of pollution lying WSW-ENE towards 39N 34W (45)
13. T+265 Profile descent at 1000ft/min to reach INBOX at FL170 (5)
14. T+270 Transit to Horta at FL170 to with 20 minute straight and level run at 230 kts for NO_x cals in clear air (60)
15. T+330 Land at Horta.

Ground power is required at Horta for one and half hours following flight.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B035	DATE: 28/07/2004	OPERATOR: Ken Dewey	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: W of the Azores in a box bounded by 35N and 43N, and 34W and 40W		PROJECT: ITOP - 146 - DC8 Intercomparison	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	psi / 90 bar	psi / 150 bar	psi / 60 bar
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 ()	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)
10:00:48	PRE	PRE	108.59	57.04	6193.65						
Remarks:											
12:34:02	GND	PRE	102.67	59.45	6104.50						
Remarks:											
14:04:00	50		100.78	59.55	6000.88						
Remarks: PRE											
14:34:10	160		97.30	60.32	5869.29						
Remarks: NOx CALS											
15:08:	220										
Remarks: PSAP FLOW ADJUSTED TO 3.0 FROM 2.0											
15:12:	220										
Remarks: TECO NOx ZERO											
15:15:00	220										
Remarks: END NOx ZERO											
15:18:30	220		99.17	58.57	5808.19						
Remarks: CLOSE TO RVP											
16:18:00	120										
Remarks: CO CAL NOx ZERO END OF COMP PROFILE											
16:19:17	120		103.31	56.72	5859.47						
Remarks:											
16:20:00	120										
Remarks: END NOx ZERO.											
16:28:51	120										
Remarks: START P4											
16:40:05	050										
Remarks: RECOMMENCE P4											
16:49	1000'										
Remarks: START RUN / CALS CO & NOx											
16:57:34	1000'		103.84	57.23	5943.12						
Remarks:											
17:33:											
Remarks: CO > NOx CALS											
:			100.43	56.28	5657.91						
Remarks: BROKE R6											
18:14:30	190										
Remarks: START CO CAL & NOx											
18:16:33			101.59	55.78	5666.21						
Remarks: F0											
18:27:	170										
Remarks: CO CAL DURING NOx CAL											
18:29:22	170		101.93	55.96	5704.13						
Remarks:											
:											
Remarks:											
:											
Remarks:											
:											
Remarks:											

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...035

Date 28/7/2004

Page 1 of 2

Start position

Video Tapes
V8
No.
Ends
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	38 31.26 N	
Long	28 42.98 W	←
Time	13:45:29	as GPS.
Status	✓	

DRS	☒
HORACE	☒
SATCOM	☒

15825

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
13 35 00		Time check AMTG with flight-deck GPS						
		- AMTG is +2 secs ahead of flight deck time						
13 52 45		T/O						
13 55 19		ASPs open, PSAP flar on						
13 58 25		Run 1 FLOGO						
14 00 53		J-U cab complete						
14 03 30		start profile						
14 11 05		end profile 1						
14 11 35		Run 2 at FL160						
14 14 15		reset turbulence probe breakers						
14 18 00		reset DCU PDATA to DLU breaker						
		Regained Pressure Height data						
14 21 37		Total under reset (no data up to this point)						
15 40 00		Time check with DC-8, AMTG = DC8 to nearest second						
15 46 25		Run 3 - good						
16 14 47		reduced profile rate to 500 ft/min						
16 36 15		reducing descent rate before end of interruption to profile						
16 40 05		restart profile 4, at 500 ft/min						
16 49 00		Run 5 at 1000 ft						
16 51 50		reduce height to 1050 ft						

200

WUXE 38/38
1531
RA DCB ETA

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B**...038.....

Date ...1.8.04.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		✓	FFSSP	✓	
Satcom C			PCASP	✓	
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	✓	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	✓	
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope	✓	
Non De-Iced		✓	SID 1	✓	
Heimann			SID 2	✓	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI		
G. Eastern			HVPS		
J. Williams			<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov			INC	X	
TWC			CCN / CNC		FWVS
FWVS		✓	CVI	X	
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear			<u>Aerosol</u>		
“ Red			PSAP		✓
“ Silieon ^{JMCL}			Nephelometer	X	
“ JO1D			AMS		✓
Lower Clear					
“ Red					
“ Silieon ^{JMCL}					
“ JO1D					
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	✓				
MARSS	✓				
DEIMOS	✓				
ARIES	✓				
SWS / SHIM	✓				
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone					
ECGC					
NOX					
CO			<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC					
PAN					
PERCA					
WAS		✓			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B035 28/07/2004

Instruments

NOT recording DRS data at start, restarted process.
Status of HORACE processes shows H-DRS-LOG - "not receiving DRS data"

Unable to display graphical pages at Flight Manager's position.

Using FM laptop to do this.

Lost some early data (just pressure height & TWC?), regained by resetting DLUs

printer cartridge running out

Aircraft